

Derivatives of Salicylic Acid. Part V. Synthesis and Constitution of 2-Nitrotoluene-6-sulphonic Acid.

A Step towards the Synthesis of 6-Sulphosalicylic Acid.

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The object of the present investigation was to synthesise 6-sulphosalicylic acid in the same way as the 4-sulpho-acid, worked out by us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 47). The present paper deals with the synthesis and constitution of the starting material, *viz.*, 2-nitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid which has been obtained in the following way.

4-Nitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid was prepared according to Jennsen (*Annalen*, 1874, 172, 230). The yield of sulphonic acid increases considerably if the sulphonation mixture is kept exposed to atmosphere. It was further nitrated so as to obtain 2:4-dinitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid. The dinitrotoluenesulphonic acid obtained by Beilstein and Kuhlberg (*Annalen*, 1870, 155, 21), as shown by the composition of the lead salts, seems to be the same as that obtained later by Schanert (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 29) and is *o*-dinitrotoluene-*p*-sulphonic acid. Unlike the sulphochloride (m. p. 125°) obtained by the above authors, the sulphochloride (m.p. 107°) in the present paper did not give the sulphonamide being susceptible to the action of alkalies and ammonia.

The alcoholic ammonium sulphide solution selectively reduces the acid and its sulphochloride to give the 2-nitro-4-aminotoluene-6-sulphonic acid and 2-nitro-4-aminotoluene-6-sulphonamide respectively.

2-Nitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid was then obtained from the above amino acid as usual *via* the diazo reaction.

That the 2-nitro-4-aminotoluene-6-sulphonic acid was produced by the partial reduction of 2:4-dinitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid was supported by obtaining the same by the sulphonation of *o*-nitro-*p*-toluidine. *o*-Nitro-*p*-toluidine was obtained by partial reduction of 2:4-dinitrotoluene with sodium sulphide (Brand, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1906, ii, 74, 470) and also by nitration of *p*-toluidine (Nölting and Collin, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 263).

It was found that 2:4-dinitrotoluene resisted all attempts at sulphonation. This is remarkable because the directing influences of the groups Me and NO₂ in 2:4-dinitrotoluene might be expected to lead to the introduction of the sulphonic acid group in the 6-position and remarkable also because the sulphonic acid in question (2:4-dinitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid) is readily produced by the nitration of 4-nitro-6-sulphotoluene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:4-Dinitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid. — *p*-Nitrotoluene-*o*-sulphonic acid (60 g.) (Jenssen, *loc. cit.*) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (120 g. *d* 1.82) and fuming nitric acid (23 g. *d* 1.51) was slowly added. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 3 hours and exposed to atmosphere when yellow crystals separated, m.p. 120°. The mixture was cooled, when a further yield of the crystals was obtained, yield 78%. (Found: N, 9.28; S, 11.02; Equiv., 3.0.2; H₂O, 11.96. C₇H₆O₇N₂S, 2H₂O requires N, 9.39; S, 10.74; H₂O, 12.08 per cent. Equiv., 298).

Lead salt.—Yellow needles. [Found: Pb, 25.98; H₂O, 8.73. (C₇H₅O₇N₂S)₂Pb, 4H₂O requires Pb, 25.84; H₂O, 8.99 per cent].

Potassium salt was prepared by adding strong potassium chloride solution to that of acid. It is slightly soluble in cold water

and readily in hot water, from which it crystallised as tiny white plates. The anhydrous salt was obtained by heating it at 180° under reduced pressure for about 2 hours. (Found: K, 11.71 ; H_2O , 10.62. $C_7H_5O_7N_2SK$, $2H_2O$ requires K, 11.60 ; H_2O , 10.72 per cent).

Sodium salt is more soluble in water than potassium salt and crystallises in small anhydrous plates. (Found : Na, 7.87. $C_7H_5O_7N_2SNa$ requires Na, 8.09 per cent).

Calcium salt is highly soluble in water from which it crystallises in small microscopic needles with 4 mols. of water. [Found : Ca, 6.34 ; H_2O , 11.58. $(C_7H_5O_7N_2S)_2Ca$, $4H_2O$ requires Ca, 6.31 ; H_2O , 11.36 per cent].

Barium salt is easily soluble in cold water from which it crystallises in long glassy white needles with $4H_2O$. When heated to 180° under reduced pressure it becomes anhydrous. [Found : Ba, 18.72 ; H_2O , 9.68. $(C_7H_5O_7N_2S)_2Ba$, $4H_2O$ requires Ba, 18.74 ; H_2O , 9.85 per cent].

The *sulphonyl chloride*, prepared from the potassium salt and phosphorus pentachloride, crystallised from benzene in small plates, m.p. 107° . It is soluble in benzene and toluene and almost insoluble in alcohol and ether, yield 6.5 g. (Found: Cl, 12.88; S, 11.53. $C_7H_5O_6N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 12.66; S, 11.40 per cent).

2-Nitro-4-aminotoluene-6-sulphonic acid.—(i) 2:4-Dinitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (100 c.c.) and 5 N-ammonium sulphide (70 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.) were added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours, when sulphur precipitated which was filtered off. On concentrating the solution the amino acid was obtained on acidifying the solution of the ammonium salt. It is sparingly soluble in water from which it crystallises in small white needles, m.p. 270° (decomp.), yield 6.5 g. (Found: N, 11.91; S, 13.87. Equiv., 233.1. $C_7H_8O_5N_2S$ requires N, 12.06; S, 13.79; per cent. and Equiv., 232).

(ii) *o*-Nitro-*p*-toluidine (5 g.) (Brand, *loc. cit.*, Nölting and Collin *loc. cit.*), was sulphonated by heating it on a water-bath with fuming sulphuric acid (20% SO_3) for 6 hours. On pouring the mixture in water white solid separated which was filtered and purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate solution and then precipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid. Decomposition temperature, analysis and derivatives agree with that of the above. The *potassium* salt crystallised from water in yellowish red stout rectangular plates.

(Found: K, 12.90; H₂O, 11.44. C₇H₇O₅N₂SK requires K, 12.75; H₂O, 11.77 per cent).

The *sulphonyl chloride* was prepared from the potassium salt (10 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (25 g.). It is soluble in benzene and toluene from which it crystallises in pale yellow needles, m.p. above 260° (decomp.), yield 7 g. (Found: Cl, 14.20; S, 12.72. C₇H₇O₄N₂ClS requires Cl, 14.19; S, 12.77 per cent).

The *sulphonamide* was obtained from the chloride and ammonia (*d* 0.880). It is soluble in water from which it crystallises in yellow plates, m.p. 230°. (Found: N, 18.16; S, 13.85. C₇H₉O₄N₃S requires N, 18.18; S, 13.86 per cent).

2-Nitro-4-diazotoluene-6-sulphonate.—2-Nitro-4-aminotoluene-6-sulphonic acid (15 g.) was diazotised at 0°. The solid separating was filtered and washed several times with cold water, yield 9 g. It is insoluble in water and explodes violently at 160° when heated slowly and at 164° when heated rapidly.

2-Nitrotoluene-6-sulphonic acid.—The above diazo compound was dissolved in alcohol and refluxed for 3 hours. On evaporating the mixture on a water-bath and then in desiccator a dark solid was obtained which is very hygroscopic. On drying this solid on a porous plate a yellow nonhygroscopic solid remains which was recrystallised from water as yellow cluster of needles, m.p. 127°. It gives dark coloured salts. (Found: N, 5.45; S, 12.57; H₂O, 14.08. C₇H₇O₅NS, 2H₂O requires N, 5.53; S, 12.66; H₂O, 14.23 per cent).

The *barium salt* is easily soluble in water from which it crystallises in dark red needles. [Found: Ba, 19.11; H₂O, 19.36. (C₇H₆O₅NS)₂Ba, 8H₂O requires Ba, 19.20; H₂O, 20.19 per cent].

The *sulphonamide* was obtained as usual by the action of ammonia on 2-nitrotoluene-6-sulphonyl chloride (liquid). It crystallised from water in white rectangular plates, m.p. 165°. (Found: S, 14.58; C₇H₈O₄N₂S requires S, 14.83 per cent).